

Relative elongation of deepwater rices

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Relative elongation of 14 deepwater rices at 1 and 2 months of submergence was studied in 3 replications at ARS, Chagharaghat, during 1981 kharif. Five seeds were sown in clay pots filled with 4 kg of a 3:1 mixture of airdried soil and farmyard manure. After 1 month seedlings were thinned to 1/pot. Three grams of urea were applied preplanting and 3 g diammonium phosphate were applied at 50 days when pots were transferred to deep water.

Height of the main culm to the highest auricle was recorded at 50 days. Plants were submerged in 50 cm water. Water level was raised 37 mm/day during the first month and 6 mm/day during the second month.

Before submergence Jalmagna check, Nang Dumto, RP31-49-2/LMN920356, Boon Nakh, Saran Kraham/RP31-49-2/LMN920349, and RP31-49-2/LMN920388

Relative elongation ability of deepwater rices, Ghagharaghat, India

Variety	Height before (cm)	Elongation	
		1-mo submergence (cm)	2-mo submergence (cm)
Jalmagna (check)	31	97	139
RP31-49-2/LMN920312	23	99	130
RP31-49-2/LMN920312-1	23	101	136
RP31-49-2/LMN920316-1	26	96	132
RP31-49-2/LMN920316-2	26	96	138
RP31-49-2/LMN920349	28	103	135
RP31-49-2/LMN920350	23	104	137
RP31-49-2/LMN920351	25	102	138
RP31-49-2/LMN920354	25	93	130
RP31-49-2/LMN920356	31	95	145
RP31-49-2/LMN920388	28	97	131
Nang Dumto	34	111	154
Saran Kraham	29	108	149
Boon Nakh	30	117	160
C. D. at 5%	4.2	6.9	7.3

were of similar, superior height (see table). After one month Boon Nakh, Nang Dumto, Saran Kraham, and RP31-49-2/LMN920350 had elongation superior to that of Jalmagna. After 2 months Boon Nakh, Nang Dumto, and Saran Kraham remained superior.

All rices had adequate, but widely

varying, elongation ability. Strains with superior growth under normal conditions were not necessarily superior under submergence. Some varieties grew faster early in submergence, but growth rate slowed later, resulting in relatively poor total performance. Further studies of this type should be conducted. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Genetics of cold tolerance at rice reproductive stage

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The genetics of cold tolerance in rice has not been adequately defined because of the complex nature of plant response to cold environments and lack of reliable methods for scoring such response.

Two sets of 21 treatments of a 6-parent diallel using IR3941-45-Plp 2B,

IR579, Himdhan, IR2637-44-2, Zenith, and IR30, and their 15 F₁s, excluding reciprocals, were grown in a randomized block design with S replications. Fifteen-day-old seedlings, raised on sand in petri dishes, were transplanted in earthen pots filled with 2 parts soil, 1 part farmyard

Estimated general combining ability effects for cold tolerance, as measured through different character indices.^a

Parent	Days to flower	Effective tillers/hill	Yield/hill	Panicle weight	Panicle length	Spikelet fertility	Panicle exertion	Pollen fertility	Crude protein	Amylose	Gelatinization temperature
IR3941-45-Plp 2B	-0.74**	-0.61	-0.83**	-5.85**	0.47**	-11.50**	-11.46**	-2.47**	-2.26**	-0.11	-0.24
IR579	1.82**	-0.93**	2.79**	11.07**	0.99**	14.86**	12.46**	4.31**	3.58**	0.54*	-0.10
Himdhan	-0.77**	-0.73**	-2.21**	-1.85**	-1.63**	-4.15**	-5.66**	-1.16**	-1.02*	-3.70**	-3.34**
IR2637-44-2	-1.41**	2.86**	-3.30**	-7.56**	-0.51**	-7.22**	-28.74**	-2.07**	2.65**	1.16**	0.33
Zenith	2.08**	0.38	5.30**	9.08**	0.73**	13.50**	38.31**	3.48**	1.20**	3.86**	2.69**
IR30	-0.98**	-0.97**	-1.75**	-4.98**	-0.05	-5.49**	-4.91**	-2.09**	-4.15**	-1.75**	0.66**
SE _{(gi)±}	0.07	0.32	0.20	0.70	0.12	0.59	1.23	0.13	0.45	0.26	0.17
SE _{(gi-gi)±}	0.11	0.49	0.27	1.09	0.19	0.91	1.90	0.20	0.69	0.40	0.25

^a*Significant at $P = 0.05$, **significant at $P = 0.01$.

manure, and 1 part sand. About 10 days before heading, one set of materials was transferred to a glasshouse chamber where temperature was maintained at 18°C. The other set was grown under normal temperature (30°C). Days to flower; effective tillers per hill; yield per hill; panicle weight, length, and exertion; spikelet fertility; pollen fertility; crude protein and amylose, and gelatinization temperature in cold stress and normal conditions were recorded. Cold injury was calculated as the difference between normal and stress conditions, expressed as a percentage of the norm.

Analysis of combining ability showed the importance of additive and dominance gene action to cold tolerance inheritance for all indices studied. Dominance effects were stronger for all characters except panicle weight and spikelet fertility. Var-

iance component analysis yielded similar results.

Proportional values among genetic components suggested there are more dominant than recessive genes. Panicle exertion and pollen fertility had asymmetrical dominant and recessive gene distributions in the parents. Symmetrical distribution was observed for the remaining indices. Positive and negative alleles at loci showing dominance were asymmetrically distributed in the parents for all cold tolerance characters studied. Combining ability analysis and genetic component analysis showed overdominance for all indices except panicle weight and spikelet fertility and pollen fertility.

IR3941-45-Plp 2B, Himdhan, IR2637-44-2, and IR30 were the best general combiners for cold tolerance (see table). Cross-

ses of IR3941-45-Plp 2B with Zenith and IR30; IR579 with Himdhan; and IR2637-44-2 with Zenith were the most promising for incorporating cold tolerance. They represented all possible combinations between parents of high, average, and low general combining ability (gca). Of these crosses, IR3941-45-Plp 2B/IR30 involved both parents with high gca and can be exploited through recurrent selection. □

ERRATUM

S. S. Malik. Gamma ray-induced semi-dwarf mutants in Basmati 370. *IRRN* 7 (6) (Dec 1982), page 4: In the column *Scnt* in the table, *No* should be changed to *Yes*.

Pest management and control DISEASES

Purification and properties of grassy stunt-associated filamentous particles

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Filamentous (6-8 nm diameter) and isometric (18-20 nm diameter) virus-like particles were found in a partially purified fraction of rice grassy stunt (GSV) infected rice plants. Filamentous particles were numerous in the fraction and isometric particles were scarce.

Filamentous particles were purified by clarification with Mg-bentonite and CCl₄, PEG treatment, and sucrose density-gradient centrifugation. Electron microscopy of the purified fraction revealed numerous filamentous particles and a few contaminants (see figure). Some filaments were circular and 200-2,400 nm long. Length distribution peaked at 1,000-1,300 nm. The UV absorption spectrum of the purified fraction was typical of a nucleoprotein

— maximum absorbance 260 nm, minimum absorbance 247 nm, and 260/280 ratio was 1.28 ± 0.3 . Filamentous particles had RNA and single coat protein of 31,000 daltons.

Antiserum was obtained by injecting rabbits with the purified filamentous particles. In the precipitin ring interface test, titer against purified filaments was 1:1280. A filamentous antigen was detected in RGS-infected leaf and RGS-exposed brown planthopper extracts diluted 1/4096 and 1/1024, respectively, by a latex agglutination test using the antiserum. The antiserum did not react

with planthopper and virus-free leaf extracts.

Purified filamentous particles were injected into the abdomen of second-instar nymphs of the brown planthopper to test infectivity of the particles. None of the injected brown planthoppers became infective.

Specific reaction between the antiserum and extracts of GSV-infected leaves and exposed insect vectors suggests that the nucleoprotein may cause GSV. Relations between the nucleoprotein and isometric particles remain to be clarified.

Electron micrograph of purified filamentous particles—X 150,000